

FAAM facility for airborne atmospheric measurements

FLIGHT FOLDER

Flight No.: B304
 Date: 09 July 2007
 Take Off 10:04:15
 Landing: 11:47:41
 Flight Time 1h43m26

Campaign: COPS

Operating Area: Baden-Baden, Germany

POB	Position	Name	Institute
1	Captain	Alan Foster	Directflight
2	Co-pilot	Ian Ramsay-Rae	Directflight
3	CCM	Gaynor Ottaway	Directflight
4	Mission Scientist 1	Phil Brown	Met Office
5	Mission Scientist 2	Paul Williams	University of Manchester
6	Flight Manager	Steve Devereau	FAAM
7	Cloud Physics	Jamie Trembath	FAAM
8	Core Chemistry / CCM2	Stuart Heath	FAAM
9	VACC 1	Barbara Brookes	Leeds University
10	VACC 2	Angela Dean	Leeds University
11	CPI 1	James Dorsey	University of Manchester
12	CPI 2	Hazel Jones	University of Manchester
13	CVI	Jeff Brown	Met Office
14	Nephelometers	Andy Wilson	Met Office
15	Mission Scientist 3	Victoria Smith	Leeds University
16	Engineer	John Kitchen	Avalon
17	Engineer	Jason Smith	Avalon
18	Transit	Al Roberts	Directflight
19	Transit	Bob Wells	FAAM
20			

Flight Track:

B304 Track 09-JUL-07

FLIGHT SUMMARY

Flight No B304
 Date: 09 July 2007
 Project: COPS
 Location: Cranfield to Baden Baden transit

Start Time	End Time	Event	Height (s)	Hdg	Comments
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095048		event	0.34 kft	123	INU NAV
095315		Start-Up	0.34 kft	123	
095712		event	0.34 kft	123	start taxi
100353		T/O	0.68 kft	216	Cranfield
100800		event	5.0 kft	043	Nevzorov zero
100934		event	5.0 kft	047	J-W zero
100959		event	5.0 kft	046	retract LBBR
101547		event	12.2 kft	020	Heimann shutter open
102354		event	24.9 kft	092	Nevzorov zero
102855	103301	Run 1	26.9 - 27.0 kft	103	210 KIAS
103448	103801	Run 2	27.0 kft	105	230 KIAS
104047	104539	Run 3	27.0 kft	106	265KIAS
114722		Land	0.37 kft	212	Baden Baden
115316		Shutdown	0.38 kft	154	48 46.90N 8 05.35E

B304 Track 09-JUL-07

Flight:

B304

KEY

- Duff Data
- Minor Problems
- OK
- Not Fitted
- Fitted, Not Operated

Thermometers

- Cabin Temperature:
- Heimann:
- Deiced Temp:
- Non-deiced Temp:

Hygrometers

- FWVS:
- General Eastern:
- Johnson Williams:
- Nevzorov:
- Total Water Probe:

Cameras

- Downward Facing:
- Forward Facing:
- Rearward Facing:
- Upward Facing:

Navigation + Aircraft

- Cruciform GPS:
- GIN Applanix:
- INU Honeywell:
- Radar Altimeter:
- RVSM IAS:
- RVSM Static Pressure:
- XR5 GPS:

Report Created 20/08/2007
17:25:13

Misc Core

- AMTG:
- AVAPS:
- Cabin Pressure:
- Fax machine:
- Printer:
- S9 Static Pressure:
- Satcom C:
- Satcom H:
- Turb Centre-Static:
- Turb Left Right:
- Turb Up-Down:
- Turb Horizontal Chk:
- Turb Vertical Chk:
- Weather Radar:
- DLUs:**
- DLU AERACK:
- DLU BBR Lower:
- DLU BBR Upper:
- DLU Core Chem:
- DLU Core Consoles:
- DLU Port Aft:
- DLU Port Fwd:
- DLU Stbd Fwd:

Radiometers

- Lower:**
- BBR (clear) Lower:
- BBR (IR) Lower:
- BBR (red) Lower:
- Upper:**
- BBR (clear) Upper:
- BBR (IR) Upper:
- BBR (red) Upper:
- ARIES:
- DEIMOS:
- IR Camera:
- JNO2 Lower:
- JNO2 Upper:
- JO1D Lower:
- JO1D Upper:
- MARSS:
- SHIMS Lower:
- SHIMS Upper:
- SWS:
- TAFTS:

Last Updated:

Cloud Probes

- 2DC:
- 2DP:
- FFSSP:
- PCASP:
- ADA:
- CCN:
- CDP:
- CIP 100:
- CIP 25:
- CPI:
- CVI:
- SID1:
- SID2:
- Aerosol**
- CPC 3025A:
- Filters 47mm:
- Filters 90mm:
- Neph - Dry:
- Neph - Wet:
- PSAP:
- AMS:
- CPC 3025 (AMS):
- INC:
- VACC:
- CPC 3010A (CVI):

01/08/2007 12:03:13

Chemistry

- CO Aerolaser 5002:
- NOx TE42C:
- Ozone TE49C:
- Ozone TE49:
- SO2 TE43C:
- TDLAS (NIR) CH4:
- TDLAS (NIR) CO2:
- FAGE:
- Formaldehyde:
- NOxy:
- ORAC:
- PAN:
- PERCA:
- Peroxide:
- PTRMS:
- TDLAS (1C):
- WAS Bags:
- WAS Bottles:
- Misc Non-Core**
- CASI/ATM:
- LIDAR:
- LTI:
- SAW Hygrometer:

MISSING LOG SHEETS:

The following log sheets are not available for flight B304:

Log	Reason
Pre-flight log	No log available
Brief	Transit so no brief
De-brief	Transit so no de-brief
Cloud Physics In Flight	Transit so no log
Cloud Physics Processing	Transit so no processing log
Core Chemistry	no In Flight log except in cases of instrument problems
VACC	VACC operator does not create a log sheet
PSAP log	No log as PSAP pump/filter info included on Flight Summary page
CPI	Transit so no log
CVI	Transit so no log
Wet Nephelometer	Transit so no log

Document control

Revision	Date	Author	Comments
r0	16 Jan 2008	Doug Anderson	Initial version missing the above noted logs
r1			
r2			

VIDEO RECORDINGS:

No video recordings were made on this flight

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